

Human Resources Motivation at Work Place: A Desideratum For Desirable behaviour Towards Achievement of Optimal Benefits In Organizations

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Abstract: Strategic human resource management demands the designation and execution of organizational strategy that enhances employee motivation. A motivated worker is an indispensable asset to any organization, private or public. Thus, the imperative of motivated employees in global competitive markets where organizations are in steady scanning of the operating environment with a view to maximizing comparative advantage cannot be overlooked. The study appraised the nature, methods and necessity for motivated workers in productive organizations. The methodology of the study is a combination of qualitative and descriptive approach. Data generated through relevant literature and structured oral interview were subjected to descriptive analysis. The findings, among other things, demonstrate that a motivated worker does not only feel highly esteemed but work unswerving towards the attainment of the organizational and employee's goals. The employee considers the organization as his/her own and ensures compliance with its code of conduct, mission, vision and objectives. The worker tends to be innovative, prudent in resource management and team spirits oriented. The cumulative result is efficiency and high rate of productivity in the affected organization. Accordingly, the study suggests that human resource managers should find the best measures to motivate their workers individually and collectively, bearing in mind that what motivate a particular worker may give a reverse result if applied to a different worker.

Key Words: *Employee, Motivation, Work place, Organization, Human resources*

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans are social beings that scarcely live and work in seclusion. The significant of people in organization is considerable because it is the people that chart, design, execute, sustain and end an organization's life. Thus, managing people in organization to achieve the mutual goals of the organization and employees is one of the most imperative management functions in an enterprise. Managers are expected to put in the time and efforts it takes to deal with complexities of workers and get them positively motivated. While some workers naturally will work hard to attain the goals set by managements, others will be on reverse course if not motivated. Employee motivation, commitment and job satisfaction are linked and dependent on each other. Effective combination of these leads to improvement in the performance of workers. An employee's motivation is a direct outcome of the totality of the employee's relationship with the management. Without a motivated workplace, organizations could face serious challenges and difficulties in achieving its mission, vision, goals and objective. Motivating employees by the management needs to be a regular routine because as a vital element at workplace, motivation leads to the performance of the units, departments and the organization in general. A motivated worker can cause increased productively and allow the company to attain higher levels of output. An employee

who is not motivated at work may waste time and resources by using working hour to pursue interests injurious to the organization.

Scholars have advanced varieties of theories in an attempt to explicate what motivates workers or how workers get motivated. Each of the models places emphasis on certain elements that may drive workers towards positive direction in organizations. Early theories embrace scientific management and Human Relation Model while contemporary theories can be classified into three: process, content and reinforcement (Aswathappa, 2002). Process theories entail Vroom's Expectancy Model, Adam's Equity Theory and Porter and Lawler's Performance satisfaction Theory whereas content theories include Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory, Herzberg's Two-factor Theory, Alderfer's ERG Theory and McClelland's Achievement-motivation Theory. Some scholars have argued that the performance of a member of an organization hinges partly on ability and partly on motivation (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2009). Accordingly, a worker must already have or be capable to learn the right mix of skills and capacities to execute a job and have to be motivated to perform the job well. It is tenable that managers who can help develop employees' skills via training, instruction, Job rotation, and so on are most likely to have a considerably higher impact on the employees' motivation. Unfortunately, some human resource managers of organizations have failed to appreciate the important of employee motivation and the need for a good motivation system. It is against this backdrop that the study intends to evaluate critically the nature, methods and necessity of having motivated workers at work place.

II. METHODOLOGY

The method of data collection employed in this work is both documentary and primary. The documentary method entails the utilization of relevant information obtained from books, internet material, conference and seminar papers, periodicals and journals written by expert scholars on employee motivation. The primary source involved information elicited via structured oral interview administered to select employees and managers from ten sampled productive organizations drawn from Enugu State, Nigeria. A total of thirty (30) employees and ten (10) managers were interviewed. The data generated from both documentary and primary sources were subjected to descriptive analysis.

III. Conceptual Clarification and Analysis

The term motivation has been given different meaning and interpretation by various scholars and writers on employee or human motivation. In its simple term, motivation is the set of forces that make people to conduct themselves in a particular manner. It is the force that ignites, directs and maintains people's behaviour (Bartol and Martin, 1998). This definition has three central elements that shape motivation. The first ingredient is ignition; the second is direction while the third is maintenance. Ignition is the initial sense of interest that an individual express towards attaining a set objective. The direction points to the set of activities that people undertake so as to attain their objective while the third component is maintenance of the behaviour until the objective is accomplished (Senyucel, 2009). The direction is determined by what a person most cherishes to do while maintenance is tantamount to the degree a person is willing to stay put in the chosen path when challenges arise (Di cesare and Sadri, 2003). For instance, if a worker is hopeful to get promotion, the worker will likely be more engrossed in working hard to persistently achieve success in his assigned task and responsibility so as to attract reward from the organization. According to Aswathappa (2002) motivation process has six stages. Motivation process according to him commences with individual's needs. Needs are felt deprivations which a person encounters at any particular period and act as motivator. These needs could be psychological, physiological and social. These deprivations compel the person to look for a way to reduce or terminate them and this constitutes the second stage in motivation. The third stage is goal direction. Motivation is goal directed and a goal is a particular outcome that the person desired to accomplish. The goals are always driving forces and achieving these goals can considerably cut down the needs. The fourth stage is performance of an individual which depends on his ability or his ability backed by motivation. $Performance = F(\text{ability} \times \text{motivation})$. A worker hoping to advance may seek to work on core challenges encountered by the enterprise so as to gain attention and influence with top managers. Promotion and praises are two strategies that organizations use to maintain desirable behavior among employee. They constitute feedback to the workers that their needs for advancement and recognition are proper. This reward stage is the fifth step while the sixth stage has to do with

re-assessment of needs deficiencies by the workers. Once the workers received either reward or punishment, they re-evaluate their needs.

Motivation and morale are closely associated concepts but they have differences. Morale has to do with the mental situation of a person obtained from his work, work group, managers, and organization he works for and environment. It generally connects to the feeling of a person's comfort, gladness and satisfaction. It is a worker's attitudes and precise reaction to his job. Morale can be high or low. High morale suggests determination at work, which is vital in accomplishing organization objectives. High morale leads to: interest in team work by the workers; organizational commitment and a sense of belongingness; immediate identification and resolution of conflict, healthy and safe work milieu; good communication; enhanced output and higher motivation. Low morale is characterized by the following: increased grievances and conflicts in an enterprise; high degree of worker absenteeism and turnover; dissatisfaction with supervisors, management and employers; poor working situations; workers disappointment; decline in output; absence of motivation (www.managementstudyguid.com). While motivation is an inner-psychological force of a person which cause the individual to behave in a particular way, morale is more of a group action. Greater motivation causes higher morale of workers whereas high morale does not essentially result in considerably motivated workers. While moral is a group concept, motivation is an individual term. Therefore, motivation takes into recognition the individual differences among the workforce. Motivation attracts primary concern in every enterprise whereas morale is a secondary event since high motivation significantly leads to higher output while high morale may not necessarily result in greater output. Things that are connected to morale are often things that are just part of the work setting but things linked to motivation are linked to the individual's performance. Motivation, as a word, is derived from "motive" meaning needs, desires, wants or drives within the persons. It is the process of activating individuals to actions so as to achieve goals. It is a psychological event which means that needs and wants of the persons have to be provided via an incentive strategy. The psychological variable that can activate the behaviour of individual can be desire for money; success; recognition; job satisfaction; team work and so on.

Figure 1: **Motivation Framework**

Source: Aswathappa(2002:314)

Iv. Intrinsic Motivation versus Extrinsic Motivation

Scholars on motivation theory tend to differentiate between intrinsic and extrinsic motivator. Nevertheless, there have been debates on the desirability of the differentiation considering the fact that one motivator can be categorized distinctively base on its context at work. Extrinsic motivation is associated with visible rewards such as salary and fringe benefits, security, promotion, contract of service, the work environment and service condition. Extrinsic motivators are those motivators that are outside the control of individuals and are noticeable

rewards such as increase in pay, bonuses and other material goods (Bratton 2007). Extrinsic motivators are usually determined at the organizational level and may considerably be beyond the control of individual manager. Extrinsic motivator can have an immediate and strong influence on the work but the effect may be temporary because they are not inherent and psychological. Extrinsic rewards are tangible and the beneficiary must satisfy the manager through his actions in order to secure the reward. They are rewards given out by another person to others.

Intrinsic motivators are those motivators that are within the control of individual and which emanate from the character of the work itself such as job satisfaction, personal development, and acknowledgement from managers or concern in a task or a project at work. Intrinsic rewards are those that come from within an individual. They are rewards that are inherent and psychologically related. Intrinsic motivators are not visible and are important to the person, such as pride. Intrinsically motivated behaviour feed the psychological needs of an individual such as competency or self worth, while extrinsic motivation has a different reward other than feeling from within a person. Intrinsic motivation is associated with internal factor. It is a motivation that stem from the need for self satisfaction and not for external reward. Intrinsic motivators are associated with quality of work life; they have the likelihood of having strong and durable impact on the individual because they are inbuilt in the individuals and not imposed by outsiders (Armstrong, 2006). Intrinsic motivators and extrinsic motivators move in different direction and are inversely proportional. As extrinsic motivators increase, intrinsic motivators decline because the individual will begin to look for external reward rather than work for self satisfaction or job satisfaction. Thus, there should be a proper mix of both motivators while emphasis should be on intrinsic motivators to really achieve feeling of self fulfillment and satisfaction

V. Theoretical Frame Work cum Theories of Motivation

There are several models that attempt to explicate motivation. These theories can be broadly classified into early theory and contemporary theory. The early theory can be subdivided into Scientific management theory and Human relation theory. Contemporary model on its part can be subsumed into two groups: content and process model. Content theories embrace Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory; Herzberg's Two-factor Motivation Theory while Process theories include Vroom's Expectancy Model; Adam's Equity theory; Porter and Lawler's Performance Satisfaction Theory. The early theory or traditional theory of management such as scientific management movement emphasizes the motivating capacity of money and material reward while the human relation model laid much stress on psychological requirement of the workers. The content approach to motivation is concerned with what motivates people to behave in a particular manner while the process approach is concerned with how people are motivated (Ezeani, 2005). The content theories attempt to explicate the actual things that really motivate the individual at work. These theories place emphasis on finding out the needs of individuals and their relative strengths and the goal they pursue so as to satisfy these needs. Thus, prominence is on the character of the needs and what motivates individuals. It is in essence about executing action to gratify needs and find out the key needs that have an effect on behaviour. An unsatisfied need creates tension and a state of disequilibrium and in order to restore balance, a goal that will gratify the need has to be identified and a behaviour path that will cause the attainment of the goal is chosen. It is not every need that is key to a person at the same time. Some may provide a much more strong drive towards a goal than the other. This is dependent on the background and prevailing circumstances of the individual (Osabiya, 2015). The process theories seek to find out the association among the dynamic variables that make up motivation and the actions desirable to affect behaviour and action. They put forward a further understanding of the intricate character of work motivation. The process theory is also called cognitive theory because it is concerned with people's perceptions of their work environment, the manner in which they interpret and understand it. Process theories concentrate on the choices or actions people take to attain their goals but content theory focus on the goals people aspire, their specific needs and explore circumstance where these needs influence behaviour. Some scholars argue that process theory provides a better approach to motivation than content theories. Cognitive theory can surely be more relevant to managers than need theory because it offers more realistic guidance on motivation techniques (Armstrong, 2006).

The tenets of the various theories of motivation as advanced by their proponents are as follows:

Scientific Management Theory: Motivation theory can be traced back to the idea of Taylor (1911) who advanced the tenets of scientific management geared toward granting greater control to management over the labour process by rewarding effort. Scientific management refers to a philosophy and set of methods that emphasized the scientific study and organization of work at the operational level so as to attain increasing efficiency. Taylor considered management superior to workers and contended that management should be the driving force of the organization. Although many scholars made useful contribution to idea of scientific management, F.W. Taylor is considered as the father of scientific management. Taylor suggested that in order to gain more, workers need to work more in the most efficient and productive way (Senyucel, 2009). Taylor assumed that there is one best way of performing job to achieve efficiency. For him, the management has to dissect the tasks in a job to ascertain the best way to perform a task so as to create the work process to follow by the employee for the purpose of attaining efficiency. Accordingly, there is need for management to plan for increased employees' performance. Several relevant techniques and principles advanced by scientific management include: scientific method of doing work; planning the task; mental revolution; time and motion studies; standardization; scientific selection, training and remuneration of worker. Taylor's approach stressed that people are basically motivated by economic rewards and will take direction if offered the opportunity to enhance the economic status. Succinctly put, Taylor's theory posits that: physical work could be scientifically studied to ascertain the best technique of performing a job; workers could be made more efficient by granting them instruction on how to execute the job; employees would not be reluctant to stick to these instructions if paid on a differential piece work basis. Nevertheless, scientific management theory has been widely criticized. The behavioural scientists contend that Taylor and his associates dehumanized employees by looking at them as ordinary factor of production that can be manipulated entirely via economic reward. Scientific management sees employees as machine that can be assembled to achieve a particular objective without regard to their physical, psychological and social well-being. Consequently, Taylor's view that workers can be motivated more by the need for money (this assumption is called rabble hypothesis) failed to take into cognizance a variety of workers' needs such as need for security, social fulfillment, esteem, and challenges task. Besides, there is no one finest way of doing a particular job.

Human Relation Theory: The origin of this theory can be traced to Elton Mayo and other human relation scholars who found that the social interactions the employees had at workplace were as well important and that the boredom and repetition of tasks were themselves motivation reducing variables. Elton Mayo who is the founder of human relation school conducted the celebrated Hawthorne experiment at the Western Electric Company in Chicago, United States of America between 1924 and 1939. The company was at that period paying above average wages, with good working condition and welfare facilities; still the management of the company was bothered about the increasing sense of dissatisfaction which prevailed among the workers. Mayo and his colleagues believe that managers could motivate employees by taking cognizance of their social needs and by making them feel useful and vital. Therefore, employee should be given liberty to make their own judgement on their job. The theory advocates that greater concentration should be given to the organization's unofficial work group. Contrary to the assumption of scientific management that workers should be seen as machine, this model see workers as human with dissimilar values and needs which must be taken into contemplation in motivating them to work towards efficiency. Human relation theory advocates more contribution of the workers in resolution making and operational process of the organization. In scientific management, employees were anticipated to reverence management's instruction for high reward based on efficient system designed by the management and implemented by the employees but in human relation model, employees were expected to act upon the management's authority because supervisors handled them with consideration and were receptive to their needs. The challenge of this model is over reliance on social contracts at work situation as motivating factor. Although social contract is a necessity, it will not at all time motivate workers.

Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory: Maslow's need hierarchy theory is classified as content theory because it used individual need to help explicate job satisfaction and work behaviour. The need hierarchy of motivation

propounded by Ibrahim Maslow contends that people are motivated and satisfied by built-in-basic intrinsic motivators that are arranged in hierarchical order. Maslow (1943), theory of motivation, proposed that people are craving beings. The theory is founded on three major presuppositions: first is that human beings have several needs that are diverse in character, ranging from biological needs at the lower ladder to psychological needs at the apex; second, individuals are in regular state of motivation, never achieving a level of satisfaction except for a very short time; third, these needs are arranged in a hierarchy so that lower level needs must be satisfied before higher level needs arise or motivate people. In fact, Maslow's need categorized human needs into five levels: Physiological needs, safety needs, belongingness and love needs, self-esteem needs, and self actualization. Each of the levels represents a group of needs not single need for each level. The most fundamental level of needs consist the primary or physiological ones. As long as the physiological needs remain unattained, they preoccupy the consciousness of the person and virtually have an exclusive power to motivate behaviour. Nevertheless, when they are attained, they cease to be motivators. The satisfaction of primary needs does not produce contentment rather it produces a fresh series of dissatisfaction. The essential needs identified by Maslow in ascending pattern of relevance are as follows:

Figure 2: Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory

Source: Aswathappa (2002: 230)

Physiological Needs: Physical survival is the most deep-seated of human needs. Physiological needs; therefore, are the vital needs of an individual which includes food, shelter, clothing, air, water etc. These needs are associated with the survival and preservation of human life and have to be fulfilled before any other level of needs. These physiological drives are directly related to the biological maintenance of the organism and must be satisfied to certain level before the person is motivated to higher level needs.

Safety Needs: Once physiological needs are attained, the next set of motives, called safety or security needs become motivators. These needs include security of lives and property, job protection, etc. The primary motivating factor is to guarantee a reasonable degree of continuity, order, structure and predictability in an individual's milieu

Belongingness and Love Need: This is the third level of needs which arise only after the attainment of physiological and safety needs. Man is sociable and as such needs to live in concord and love with others or work in accord and love with co-workers in a work place. A person motivated on this level of needs long for affectionate relationship with others both in family and work place. Being loved leads to vigorous feeling of worth and enhance commitment to productivity, while not being loved gives rise to sense of futility, hostility and exhibition of resistant, antagonist and non corporative behaviour which challenge performance.

Self-esteem: Maslow grouped these into two sets. Self respect and esteem from others. The former embraces things such as desire for competence, confidence, personal strength, adequacy, achievement, independence and freedom. Esteem from others embraces prestige, recognition, acceptance, attention, status, reputation and appreciation. Satisfaction of the self-esteem need produces feelings and attitude of self-confidence, worth,

strength, capability and of being useful and relevant in the world while the reverse will lead to feelings and attitude of inferiority, ineptitude, weakness and helplessness. In work place, self-esteem need relate to job title, merit pay, supervisory recognition, personal encouragement etc. Self esteemed workers demonstrate commitment to organizational goals and objective.

Self-actualization Needs: These are needs of the highest level and these needs are found in those persons who have achieved other four levels of needs. To be self-actualized is to become the kind of person you want to be, to attain the highest level of your potential. According to Maslow this has to do with the desire to become everything that one is capable of becoming.

Hertzberg's Two-Factor Theory: The theory inquired into job-related satisfaction and dissatisfaction factors. The model which is termed dual factor theory, the motivation-hygiene theory and two-factor theory has been largely accepted by managers dealing with challenges of human behaviour at work. The theory was the outcome of vital interviews carried out in the 1950s by Herzberg. He interviewed 200 engineers and accountant in the Pittsburg area of United States of America. The interviewees were asked to explain actions which had caused them to feel "exceptionally good or exceptionally bad" at work. Responses from the interviewees revealed that factors that made them feel good were entirely distinct from those that made them sad. Intrinsic factors such as achievement, the work itself, responsibility, advancement and growth make workers feel exceptionally good or satisfied. These factors are variously referred to as motivators, satisfiers or job-content factors. On the other hand, factors such as company policy and administration, supervision, working condition; salary, security, and interpersonal relation make them feel bad or not satisfied. These factors Hertzberg called dissatisfiers, hygiene or maintenance factors. They are dissatisfiers and not motivators. According to Hertzberg, satisfaction and dissatisfaction are not opposite poles of one dimension but rather two separate dimensions. Satisfaction is caused by motivators while dissatisfaction is caused by hygiene factors. To achieve satisfaction managers must cope with both satisfiers and dissatisfiers, improve hygiene factor. When dissatisfaction is removed from the feeling of workers, it creates a frame of mind for motivation. With the provision of satisfier, motivation is triggered off. Hygiene factors do not engender job satisfaction but engender good working conditions that offer good hygiene. Hygiene factors are extrinsic and they condition the environment that work occurs while motivational factors are intrinsic (Herzberg, 1966). Hertzberg argued that money is not the most powerful force on job but rather the content of job that are primarily related to work motivation.

ERG Theory: ERG theory represents existence, relatedness and growth. ERG Theory advanced by Alderfer (1969) contends in line with Maslow that individuals have needs that are set in order of hierarchy. He also believes that needs are crucial determinant of human behaviour. Nevertheless, he criticized Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory for being firmly segmented and difficult to differentiate the level of importance of need. Consequently, he grouped the needs into three categories: Existence, Relatedness and Growth (ERG). Existence needs consist of Maslow's physiological and safety needs; relatedness need comprise all Maslow's social needs and some of the esteem needs. Growth needs are identical with Maslow's self actualization needs where individuals attain their full potential in life. In other words, ERG theory varies from Maslow's hierarchy of needs in three aspects. First Alderfer categorized needs into three hierarchies instead of five stipulated by Maslow. Second, the need hierarchy theory assumes a rigid step-like progression, while ERG theory assumes that more than one need may be in action at the same time. That is to say, that Alderfer implies that there is no firm hierarchy where a lower-level need has to be gratified before the next level. An individual, therefore, can be working for growth notwithstanding that existence or relatedness needs remain unsatisfied. Alderfer believes that it is not necessary for one level of need to be attained before the materialization of other level of needs. Thus, his submission that diverse needs can run concomitantly owing to complicated nature of human beings. Third, Maslow had contended that an individual will remain at a particular level until that need is attained but ERG theory maintains that when a higher level need becomes unattainable, the person's desire to enhance a lower-level need occurs. ERG does not essentially subscribe to the nature of a hierarchy of needs but rather contended that all classes of needs are active in persons and are not set in order of their significant (Senyucel, 2009). One important note in ERG theory is the frustration-regression hypothesis which proposes that frustration

of a higher level need can set off regression to a lower level need. That is to say that the inability to achieve a particular class of needs can lead to increase of significance of other individual's needs.

Achievement Motivation Theory: David C. McClelland and his associate were the advocates of the achievement motivation theory also known as three needs theory or needs theory of motivation. The theory identified three types of basic needs and motives which are of paramount significant to persons and act as factors which affect behaviour and reactions. The theory suggests that each individual has a need for all the three factors (power, affiliation and achievement) but that individuals differ in the extent to which the various needs motivate their behaviour and reactions. On the Need for Achievement (n/ACH) the theory states that workers with a high need for achievement obtain satisfaction from attaining their set of goals or objectives. Success at a task is vital to the high achievers. Workers with high need for achievement like challenging task, like inventiveness, have passionate desire for success and an equally extreme fear of failure, tend to be restive, like to work long hours, set goal for themselves, prefer to assume personal responsibility to get a job done, detest task with high risk, abhor easy task. Although people with a high need for achievement are often affluent; their wealth is an outcome of their aptitude to attain goals. In most societies, goal achievement is financially rewarded. High achievers are not motivated by money per se rather money is the indicator of their achievement. McClelland assumes that the need for achievement can be learned.

On the need for power (n/PWR), the theory states that workers demonstrating the needs for power derive satisfaction from the ability to control others. Such individual seek positions of leadership, enjoy decision taking, like exercising authority, influence and control, have good ideas, enjoy teaching and public speaking, are forceful, outspoken and demanding, use initiative (Ezeani, 2005). Actual attainment of goal is less significant than the means by which the goals are attained. Organization such as military and political organization that foster a power motive attracts people with a high need for power. As for Need for Affiliation (n/AFF) McClelland postulates that individuals showing affiliation needs as dominant motive obtain satisfaction from social and interpersonal activities. They derive joy from being loved, enjoy being a member of a team or club, always ready to sympathize and assist others in need, exhibit care, good at relating with others, loyal to his group, respect group norms and values.

McGregor's Theory X and Y: Douglas McGregor motivated by Maslow's theory of need generated ideas on workers motivation where he propounded Theory X and theory Y assumptions which assert that manager's views and disposition about people affects the way they manage. McGregor (1957) posits that the behaviour of a manager as the leader would be affected by the specific set of beliefs he holds: Theory X and theory Y. Theory X represents the set of assumptions that individuals are motivated only to satisfy their elementary needs and not to add to the satisfaction of organizational needs. Theory X suggests that individual only work for money and they are naturally untrustworthy and fancy to do as little as possible at work. When this circumstance arises, McGregor contends that managers attempt to change their staff behaviour to suit the organizational needs via punishment, control and reward. The theory X managers have the following assumption about their workers: the average human being has inbuilt dislike of work and will avert it if he can; because of this human disliking of work most individuals must be forced, directed or threatened with sanction to get them put adequate effort towards the attainment of organizational objectives; average human being prefers to be directed, wishes to be shown task, has relatively small aspiration and need security above all. On the other hand, theory Y represents a set of assumptions that individuals are motivated for growth and fulfillment and that they can be trustworthy to contribute to the accomplishment of the goals of organizations. According to this Y theory, the responsibility of managers is to enable workers to develop and grow at work through creating a fitting work condition which can be achieved in various manners such as offering training and development opportunities, modifying job design or changing certain job task. In other words, theory Y managers assumes that: performing cerebral and corporeal task is as natural as play or rest; outside control and threat of sanction are not the only way of bringing about endeavor toward organizational objective; man exercises self direction and self principle in the service of objectives to which his is committed; commitment to objectives is a function of the reward attached to their achievement; average human beings learn under proper conditions, not only to accept but to seek responsibility; the ability to exercise a pretty high level of thoughts, ingenuity and creativity in solving the challenges of

organization is broadly distributed in the population; under the circumstances of contemporary industrial life, the intellectual potentialities of the average human beings are only partially utilized. Whereas managers holding theory Y are likely to be democratic, those holding theory X assumptions tend to be autocratic.

Expectancy Theory: Expectancy theory is classified as process theory which concentrates on the choice or actions individual make to attain their goals. The expectancy model is also referred to as instrumentality theory, path-goal theory and valence-instrumentality-expectancy theory. This theory consists of a set of assumptions that was advanced by Vroom (1964) and Porter and Lawler (1968). Vroom (1964) criticized Herzberg's two-factor theory as being too reliant on content and context of the work roles of the people being interrogated. Expectancy theory is founded on the assumption that work effort is generally towards behaviours that people believe will lead to desired outcome. The basic premise of the theory is that workers are rational and not impulsive. They reflect on what they have to do to gain reward and how much the reward mean to them before they execute their task. Thus, motivation is dependent on an individual's expectancy of accomplishing an objective which has value for him. Four significant variables need to be explicated to appreciate the expectancy model better. These valuables are first level and second level outcomes, expectancy, valence and instrumentalities.

First level and second level outcomes: performance accomplished due to efforts is the first level outcome. Performance may be reflected via productivity, absenteeism, quality of work etc. Second level outcomes are the rewards (positive or negative) that the first level outcomes are likely to generate. They embrace a pay rise, promotion, peer acceptance and job security. Expectancy is the assumption that there is a link between effort and performance. It is the belief that a particular effort will attract a particular level of performance. Expectancy demonstrates an individual's evaluation of the probability that a given action will or will not produce a particular result. Expectancy can be restated as follows: Effort-to-outcome. Instrumentality on the other hand is a perception that performance related outcomes will result in value related outcomes. It is a perception that first level outcomes are connected with second level outcomes. In other words, instrumentality is the association between the first level outcome and the second level outcomes. Instrumentality can be stated as follows: Performance-to-outcome. Besides, Valence is the expected value of outcomes. It is the strength of a person's desire for particular results or outcome. Valence can have values ranging from negative to positive. It may be positive that is outcome desired; zero that is outcome is neither desired nor unattractive; negative that is outcome is unattractive. Outcomes with positive valence include respect by friends and co-workers, job security, earning enough money while outcomes with negative valence are things like being laid off, lack of promotion and respect at work place. According to the expectancy theory, motivation is: $\text{Expectancy} \times \text{instrumentality} \times \text{valence}$ or force (Motivation) = valence X expectance, if any one of the variables is low, motivation will probably be low.

Equity Theory: Adams (1965) equity theory focuses on the belief that persons' perception of how justly they are treated when related to others will influence their motivation. Equity theory is a process theory. It is alternatively called social comparison theory or the inequity theory. The theory assumes that individuals are motivated by their desire to be fairly treated in their relationship at workplace. When workers work for an enterprise, they basically exchange their service for pay and other benefits. The theory posits that individual attempt to reduce any inequity they may perceive as a consequence of this exchange association. Adams (1965) suggests that workers place a value on various input (eg effort, time, skills) and outputs (salary, acknowledgement). If a worker thinks that the input he puts into a task supersedes the output (outcome) then the worker will be dissatisfied and he will be motivated to change the situation by either working less or asking for a pay rise. If a worker perceived that he is either overpaid or underpaid, they will be motivated to restore equity. When attempting to reduce inequity; the worker may resort to several alternative which include altering his input, altering his outcome, distorting his inputs and outcomes cognitively, heaving the field etc. It is not that the worker or person feeling inequity alone gets motivated to restore equity; the person with a feeling of equity gets motivated to maintain the prevailing circumstance.

Goal Setting Theory: The basic belief of goal-setting theory is that workers' goals determine their behaviour at workplace. Locke (1968) contends that workers will be satisfied if they attain their goals and the more difficult

these goals are to accomplish, the more satisfied employees will be when they accomplish them. Moreover, goals with clear and explicit outcomes are likely to cause higher performance. For instance, a worker is likely to perform better if the outcome of the task is known and clearly explicated rather than general goals. It also contends that effective communication or feedback will lead to enhanced employee performance. Effective feedback on the outcome of a task will enable the employee to spot his strength and weakness and will cause him to be more conscious of his performance next time. Researches have revealed that the higher the employees are involved in setting goals, the more productive is their performance. This can be achieved through down-top approach instead of top-down approach to goal setting. By getting the employees involved in setting goal, the employees feel sense of belonging and this will be motivated.

From the above discussions, it is obvious that there is no simple motivation model that can comprehensively explicate employee behaviour at work. Human beings are complex and unique and thus are motivated by different factors. It is left for human resource practitioners and managers to find out what motivate their different workers and work towards their application as they suit each employee. In order words, human resources managers should rise up to the challenge of finding the finest measure or combination of models to motivate their employee individually and collectively since what motivate a particular employee to enhance performance may motivate the other to reduce performance.

VI. Employee Motivation Techniques: Principles, Merits and Limitations

Knowledge about the models of motivation, though essential, is not adequate to motivate workers at work place. Human resource managers have to keep abreast of the specific methods which could help the manager motivate his workers or subordinate since each technique has its challenges and value. Below are some of the motivation techniques:

Reward: People join organization in anticipation of reward. Firms give out money and other benefits in swap for the employee's availability, capacity and behaviours. Organizational recompense system include membership and seniority; task performance, competency and job status. Under membership and seniority-based rewards, a higher-ranking employee receives higher benefits than low-ranking employees. Pay rise, advancement, retirement benefits and perquisites depend on employees' rank. Although seniority-based reward attracts applicants, it may perhaps not straightforwardly motivate performance. This reward type tends to diminish turnover but possibly will fail to motivate achievers to perform better. One more problem is that membership-based reward discourages poor performers from voluntarily leaving the organization because alternative job are simply unavailable to them. Under job status-based reward structure, organization rewards employee according to the status they hold. Their jobs are evaluated to establish differentials in status of jobs which forms the criterion for determining salaries and wages differentials. Job that demands more skill and effort, have more responsibility and difficult working condition would have more worth and thus would attract higher pay grade. High status job holders receive higher reward and perquisite. One advantage of this type of reward is that it helps to maintain feeling of equity. Job evaluation system attempts to ensure internal equity; that is to make the employees feel that their pay is fair when related to how much other jobs in the firm are paid; while pay survey help to ensure external equity; that is ensure that workers feel their pay is fair when related to how much people in other firms are paid (Steven, and Many Ann, 2000).

Job-based rewards motivate workers to compete for higher position in the hierarchy of the firm. Nevertheless, job-based reward does not motivate achiever to perform better because employees are rewarded not based on performance attain but on status. Under competency-based reward, employees are anticipated to have a lot of competencies and these capacities are assessed by observing particular pattern of behaviour. Competencies are demonstrated via skills, knowledge and traits that lead to desirable behaviour. Where rewards are associated with employees' competences, what emerges is the skill-based pay. In the skill based-pay, workers are paid on the grounds of the number of jobs they are able to execute or on the degree of their knowledge. The rational for this system is to motivate workers to gain further skills so that they become more relevant to the enterprise. Competency-based rewards have advantages. They have been eulogized for developing a better-skilled and flexible workforce. Customers' needs are attained to more quickly. Workers can

handle any job with felicity. Quality of product and service tends to improve because the workers have several skills. Nevertheless, competency based system causes disparities which may de-motivate workers. The system is also expensive to operate. Under performance-based rewards system employees' pay is associated with performance instead of seniority or membership. Performance-based rewards are many but the most common among them are: Organizational rewards (profit sharing; stock option); Team rewards (Gain sharing and special bonuses); individual rewards (piece rate, commission, merit pay, bonuses). Profit sharing is an organizational performance-based reward. In profit sharing, designated workers are permitted to share in the profit made by the enterprise. Employees stock option schemes (Esops) confer ownership of the firm on employees. It motivates employees to acquire shares of the firm and reward them by way of dividend and market appreciation of the shares. Team rewards are common where firms depend on group to get the work done. Some teams are rewarded with special bonuses or gifts if they jointly attain particular goals. A gain sharing plan is a type of team reward that motivates team members to reduce the cost and increase labour efficiency in their work process. Gain sharing plan utilizes a pre-designed formula and calculate cost saving and pay bonus to all team members. Basically, the company shares the cost savings with employees. Individual rewards are very common in companies. The most common is the piece rate which associate pay to units produced by a worker. Commissions are paid to sales agents on the actual sales made by them. Merit pay is based on an individual's performance. This is gradually substituted by re-earnable bonuses for achieving particular tasks or for accomplishing certain goals. It has been argued that even though momentary reward is a powerful motivator, money cannot motivate some individuals under certain circumstances (Aswathappa, 2002).

Job Enlargement: Job enlargement refers to increasing the number of diverse tasks executed by workers in a single job. For instance, if a teacher moves from only teaching the students to teaching the students and involvement in school administration, his job has been enlarged. Job enlargements try to add similar tasks to the job so that it will have more variety and be more captivating. In other words, job enlargement entails adding to the scope of a job by widening the range of tasks and responsibilities within the same level and border. It involves performing a diversity of job or operation at the same time. Job enlargement helps an organization to enhance and increase the skill of the worker to organization as well as the individual benefit. It improves the learning capacity of the worker since the worker gain skills on many new activities. Thus, it provides wide range of activities for the worker. Job enlargement can motivate workers through task variety, meaningful work modules, ability utilization, worker-paced control and performance feedback. Nevertheless, job enlargement has some limitations and demerits. It tends to be a costly affair because the workers may require additional training for their enlarged job. In other words, it increases production cost of an organization. Moreover, productivity may decline in the short run owing to initiation of new system. Employee-unions usually demand increase pay owing to increase work load.

Job Enrichment: Job enrichment is a technique of motivating workers where a job is designed to have interesting and challenging tasks which can require more skill and enhance pay. It is a management concept that requires designation of jobs so that they become more challenging to the workers and have less repetitive work. The reason for job enrichment is to make the job more satisfying to the worker. The general organizational goal often includes increasing worker job satisfaction, reducing turnover, and improving productivity of workers. Job enrichment involves giving an employee additional responsibilities previously assigned to his managers or superior authority. In essence, an enriched job gives the worker more self-management in his task. While job enrichment gives workers vertical authority, job enlargement gives them horizontal authority. A primary characteristic of job enrichment is authority, meaning that the worker has less duty to report on his task to his superior. Companies use enrichment as a way of enhancing the organizational morale. The more valuable or sense of belonging an employee feels, the more motivated they are to produce maximum result. Through job enrichment workers learn more vertical skill that prepares them for higher level position and management. Workers are more mentally activated when they have authoritative, decision-making control over their job. This enables them to be mentally focused on their tasks and the organizational objectives. Ambitious workers are more likely to remain with the organization if they are trusted to perform higher level responsibilities.

Therefore, advantages of job enrichment could be highlighted as follows: it makes the job interesting by removing boring and monotony; it helps in reducing the rate of employee turnover and absenteeism; it motivates the workers by giving them opportunity for self actualization through growth and development; it makes task enforcement easy and enhance workers skills; it gives more job satisfaction to the worker; it makes the worker more creative when they work in an enriching challenging jobs; it leads to qualitative and quantitative improvement in output. Nevertheless, job enrichment as a motivating technique has some limitations. The first major challenge is that most of the workers do not want the type of changes initiated by job enrichment. They do not want challenging job. Secondly, job enrichment, is limited to unskilled and semiskilled jobs because jobs for highly skilled professionals already have many challenging aspects. Moreover, technology may not allow the enrichment of all jobs. With specialized machinery, tasks and processes, it may not be plausible to make the job very meaningful. Job enrichment is an expensive programme that adds to the cost of production. It requires additional training which cost resources that exceed the gain in productivity. Sometimes, the worker may prefer to have job enrichment but lack required capabilities and qualifications to tackle the new challenges. Another, disadvantage is that there is tendency on the part of management to impose enrichment on workers instead of seeking the consent of workers. This will have adverse impact on the workers.

Job Rotation: Job rotation entails shifting a worker from one job to another. It is a management technique for motivation where workers are shifted between two or more assignment and jobs at regular intervals of time in order to expose them to all verticals of an organization. It is a predetermined method with an objective to test the worker skills and capabilities in order to place the worker at the right position. The objectives of job rotation include: testing employee skills and competencies; developing a wide range of work experience; exposing employees to all verticals of the company; creating right worker job fit; succession planning; reducing monotony of the job. Thus, the first and uppermost objective of job rotation is to reduce the monotony and repetition involved in a job. It permits workers to experience diverse type of jobs and motivate them to perform well at each level of job replacement. Also, it develop a pool of workers who can be promoted to high level of management if someone retires or leaves the company, that is succession planning. The success of organization depends on fixing the correct people at the correct place or position. Job rotation aims at fixing a correct person in correct vacancy. Besides, through job rotation the workers are bared to different vertical positions in an organization and the operations concerned at the different levels. It gives them opportunity to comprehend the working of the organization and different issues that emanate while working. Testing and analyzing workers skills and competencies and then allocating them the work that they excel at is a major role of job rotation process. This is achieved by moving them to different job and assignments and finding their competencies and capacity so as to place them where they are at best in enhancing productivity..

Despite its gains, job rotation has its limitation. Rotating job too swiftly or too recurrent may hinder a worker from developing strong skill in any job area. The worker becomes a jack of all trade, but a master of none. This limits a worker's capacity to increase productivity or performance in each given job function. When workers skills are not developed owing to job rotation, the workers miss the opportunity to move upward in position at workplace or department. Moreover, job rotation exposes the workers to safety risks. Constant changes in use of equipment and tools may cause accident because the worker lacks familiarity with safety procedure and proper usage (Kokemuller, 2017). It increases training cost, and disrupt work process since rotated workers take time to adjust to a new set up.

Empowerment: Empowerment is one of the ways to motivate workers. Empowerment is an approach to leadership that empowers subordinates as a key component of managerial and organizational effectiveness. Empowerment is a technique of increasing sense of self-efficacy among members of an establishment by given workers authority and liberty to make decision which motivate them to realize and employ their full potential. Empowered employees are passionate and actively hardworking. Thus, having more control over their own job is the key propelling force of empowerment that enhances growth and improved productivity. Empowerment makes the workers to fell being valued and that their feedback on performance is appreciated by the organization. Empowerment consist of five steps: identification of conditions of powerlessness; implementation of empowerment strategies and techniques; removal of conditions of powerlessness and provision of self-

efficacy information; generating feeling of empowerment; empowerment result in performance. Employee participation and empowerment is concerned with the contributions of workers in administration and decision taking in respect of organizational policies, objectives and strategies. Empowerment takes place when decision making power and authority to allocate resources are given to the workers who then develop a sense ownership and control over their jobs. Empowered worker feel more responsible, put more initiative and creativity in their work and enjoy challenging work. Empowerment demands team formation. Teams are self-directed or simply empowered team. Sharing of information is also necessary for empowerment. Workers have to be notified about the business and shown how their work fit-in. Relevant tips for empowering workers include: transferring responsibility with authority to the worker; replacing the role of stringent managerial control with that of partnership role; tolerating mistakes made by subordinates; sharing information with subordinates; allowing team formation; giving feedback on performance to workers. Through empowerment, customers' satisfaction can be obtained since the empowered employees can swiftly take decision to solve problems without demanding instruction from the superior. Besides, enhanced freedom improves productivity and enhances worker's capacity and motivation to face new challenges and solve them. Adequate remuneration with empowerment is necessary for an organization that seeks to get greater commitment and trust from its members. If the workers are loyal to the establishment and greatly motivated, managerial levels of effectiveness and growth can be attained by the establishment. Although empowerment is essential, it has to be executed with care. Where workers suffer from too much ego and are greatly egocentric, empowerment does not make sense. Moreover, where workers express the feeling that they are to be led and not to lead, empowerment does not motivate them. The same scenario applies to where employees have phobia for challenging job.

Goal setting: Goal setting is one of the most effective and largely practiced approaches to motivation of employees. Goals are the immediate or ultimate objective that workers are attempting to achieve from their work efforts in organizations. Goal setting, therefore, is the process of motivating workers by setting performance goal. A worker who has no intelligible view of what he wants to achieve in an organization tend to relax his effort. Therefore, clear goals, tends to enhance performance since the employee will put more efforts to achieve the set target. Nevertheless, this does not suggest that without a goal, employee preference is zero. Goals and motivation are interrelated in several ways. Goals motivate workers to weigh against their present performance with the goals and as such when the workers feel that they fall below the expectation of the goals, they feel discontented and work harder to accomplish the goal. Similarly, when workers do well in achieving a goal, they feel contented and competent; such emotions are relevant and can be a source of strong incentive to put more efforts to work. Moreover, the establishment of a goal makes clear the level of performance needed and once this level is established, individual can focus on setting effective strategy for achieving it. Goal setting theory stresses the relevance of self-efficacy; that is the belief of individual in his capability to perform at given levels. People who have self-assurance in themselves are motivated and improve performance to achieve the set goals. The theory also shows that goals direct behaviour only when they are accepted by self and others. If other workers do not recognize the goals, performance of a worker will not get better. Also, if the goal is not acceptable to the self, its effect on the behaviour of the worker will be undersized. For goals to impact on employee performance, goals have to fulfill certain requisites: goal specificity, goal commitment, goal acceptance, organizational supports.

VII. Features of Sound Employee Motivation System

Good motivation techniques have some attributes which are vitals for motivation to achieve its key objectives of enhancing the efficiency of the workers for the purpose of accomplishing the goals of the individuals and organizations. A sound motivation method should give reasonable reward and recognition to better-quality performance. In other words, the motivation technique should be designed in such a way that workers' outstanding performance or contribution should be duly compensated and acknowledged. Also, the motivation system must be associated with the goals of the organization. Hence, the goals of employees must be aligned with that of the organization. This means that organizational goals and employees' goals have to be integrated into the motivation strategy. Another attribute of good employee motivation system has to do with participatory

decision making. The management approach should be that which encourage the involvement of the subordinates and employees in decision making process. The management should seek the view of their subordinate in making decision that effects the organization and workers. Moreover, sound motivation system must handle the complaints, grievances and challenges faced by the workers with fairness. The employees have to be handled in fair and just manner.

Motivation method must be very effective and efficient for it to be considered appropriate. It must be an approach that achieves its objective at minimal costs. Besides, the motivation system should involve monetary as well non monetary rewards. The pecuniary reward should associate with performances. Performance should be based on the employees' action towards the goals of the organization and not on the fame of the appraised employee. There should also be sanction for employees that perform below expectation. In other words, carrot (reward) and stick (punishment) technique should be applied to motivate both efficient and inefficient employees. The system should hearten supportive supervision whereby the supervisors share their views and experiences with their subsidiaries. The supervisors listen to their subsidiaries' views and assist them in the performance of the designated job. The manager approach should be based on motivate yourself to motivate your employees.

VIII. Necessity for Employee Motivation System

Employee motivation is a desideratum for organizations particularly in contemporary competitive global market where the continued existence of any organization hinges on the efficiency and effectiveness of its human resources competence, which gives it comparative advantage. An organization without sound motivation system tends to engender workers that are liabilities and sources of downfall. Motivation apart from being a source of strength to individual workers and organization is a driving force towards efficient and effective service delivery. Below are some of the significance and contributions of workers' motivation toward mutual benefits in organizations:

Reduction of Wastage and Damage: Motivated workers tend to take great caution in handling the working tools of the enterprise. They utilize the operation machines with great care to curtail or do away with causing damage to the machinery. This is of benefit to the organization because it reduces production outlay which stems from repairing or replacing damage tools.

Reduction of industrial accident: A motivated worker tends to work with carefulness and observe the operational guide. The adherence to safety rule tends to reduce the rate of accidents which may occur if workers are not psychologically balance owing to work place related matters.

Corporate Image: Motivated employees are more loyal and unwavering to the enterprise. They work with unfathomable sense of commitment and dedication. This enhances the overall performance of the employee which adds to the benefit of the organization. Motivated workers protect and defend the image of the organization. They stand for the culture of the organization and this result in better relations with all the stakeholders.

High Sense of esteem and belonging: A motivated worker does not only feel highly esteemed but work unswerving towards the attainment of the organizational and employee's goals. The employee considers the organization as his/her own and ensures compliance with its code of conduct, mission, vision and objectives

Enhanced Innovation: Motivation promotes the innovative and ground breaking capacity of the employees. Motivation permits the workers to employ their initiatives to find out novel procedure in the performance of their operation. Such employees that are motivated are ingenious and exceptionally useful for the organization to gain comparative advantage over other competitors in the competitive market.

Decline in Absenteeism and Employee Turnover: Motivated workers are less likely to be involved in absenteeism because of their keen for their job. Moreover, they may not want to leave the organization in exploration of another because of the profound sense of belonging which they have cultivated towards the enterprise. Thus, motivated workers are passionate to be at the work place at the appropriate time and execute their tasks with grand passion.

Harmonious Relation and team work: Motivated workers tend to interact congenially in an organization. Motivation helps to trim down labour grievance and disputes. It guarantees sound relation between the management and labour. Therefore, there is harmonious industrial relation which enhances the overall efficiency of the organization. Moreover, motivation improves the team spirits of workers and thus improves the work setting and general performance of the workers and organizations

Optimum Utilization of Resources/efficiency: Motivation leads to high self-esteem and enhanced productivity. It leads to greater employee involvement and lesser wastage. This leads to maximum utilization of the organizational resources. The cumulative result of motivation is efficiency and high rate of productivity in the affected organization. Indeed, motivated workers tend to ensure that the human and material resources of the organization are optimally exploited for the mutual benefit of the organization, workers and society.

IX. CONCLUSION

Human resources are vital to the success of the organization. In global competitive market, where organizations are in constant scanning of the operating setting with a view to gaining comparative advantage, motivated workers are greatly essential. Thus, for an organization to achieve its goals and that of the employees there is need for adoption of suitable motivation techniques that will stimulate the morale of the workers, give them sense of belonging; and enhance their loyalty, commitment and dedication to the attainment of set out goals for the mutual benefit of the organizations, employees and society. Human resource managers must endeavour to find out the motivator for each worker since what motivates workers differs from one person to the other. In order words, there is no standardization in what motivate every worker and as such human resources managers should have the capacity to identify and utilize any factor or combination of factors that motivate each worker in his organization.

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